

Insights into Air Quality and Mixed Gas Analysis: A Machine Learning and Visualization Approach

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Abstract: The widespread threat of air pollution looms over our cities, silently endangering both human health and the environment. In response, this project delves into a comprehensive analysis of air quality metrics and pollutant data sourced from the CPCB website of India. By meticulously examining these datasets, we aim to uncover crucial insights into pollution trends and identify the primary pollutants contributing to environmental degradation. Our approach extends beyond analysis, as we strive to translate these insights into actionable information accessible to the public, policymakers, and stakeholders through an intuitive website interface featuring interactive dashboards. In the realm of air quality prediction, we leverage advanced machine learning algorithms, including Random Forest, Linear Regression, Decision Tree, XGBoost, K-nearest neighbours (KNN), and Lasso Regression. These models empower us to forecast air quality trends with precision and assess the environmental impact of mixed gas reactions. Furthermore, our study delves into the intricate dynamics of mixed gas interactions in chemical reactions, focusing particularly on five key gases, carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), methane (CH₄), and ammonia (NH₃). Through rigorous analysis and visualization techniques, we explore how varying proportions of these gases influence the formation of diverse chemical products and their potential harmfulness. By combining empirical data analysis with sophisticated modeling techniques, our project aims to provide valuable insights and tools for combating air pollution and safeguarding both human health and the environment.

Keywords: Air quality, Mixed gas analysis, Machine Learning models, Visualization, Predictions, CPCB (Central Pollution Control Board)

I. INTRODUCTION

Air pollution presents a widespread and escalating issue in the modern age, arising from various anthropogenic sources, including industrial operations, transportation, and the combustion of fossil fuels. This widespread contamination of the atmosphere results in the emission of hazardous pollutants, encompassing carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), particulate matter (PM), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), ozone (O₃), and more. These pollutants not only pose a threat to human health but also cast a shadow on the ecological balance, impacting both animals and plants. The far-reaching implications of air pollution range from respiratory diseases like bronchitis and lung cancer to broader environmental concerns such as global warming, acid rain, and climate change. Furthermore, it exacts a heavy economic toll on societies and leads to an array of contemporary environmental issues, including reduced visibility, smog, aerosol formation, and premature deaths.

Scientists and researchers have recognized that air pollution extends its adverse effects even to historical monuments. Emissions from vehicles, industrial facilities, agricultural practices, and power plants contribute to the emission of greenhouse gases, which, in turn, exacerbates climate conditions and disrupts plant-soil interactions. These climatic fluctuations have repercussions not only on human and animal populations but also on agricultural productivity, leading to significant economic losses.

Furthermore, contemporary environmental research has expanded its focus to encompass mixed gas analysis, recognizing that the gases present in the atmosphere has multifaceted effects on both human health and the environment. These mixed gases include volatile organic compounds (VOCs), heavy metals, and other chemical constituents. The monitoring and analysis of mixed gases are essential for gaining a comprehensive understanding of air quality and its impact on public health.

The Air Quality Index (AQI), a critical parameter for assessing air quality, is closely linked to public health. A higher AQI level signifies greater exposure to dangerous pollutants, underscoring the urgency of predicting and monitoring air quality. This is particularly crucial in urban areas undergoing rapid industrial and motorized development. While many air quality studies and research initiatives are directed towards developing countries, where concentrations of deadly pollutants like PM_{2.5} are disproportionately high, limited attention has been devoted to air quality prediction in Indian cities. Therefore, there is a compelling need to bridge this gap by analysing and predicting AQI for India.

In response to this pressing issue, our research project takes a comprehensive approach to address the multifaceted problem of air quality. Utilizing data from the Central Pollution Control Board of India (CPCB), our study focuses on three critical aspects: air quality visualization, pollution prediction, and in-depth analysis of mixed gases in the atmosphere. Central to our project is the development of a user-friendly web-based platform for visualizing air quality data, empowering the public and policymakers to monitor air pollution trends and make informed decisions. Notably, our project integrates advanced machine learning models for precise pollution level prediction. These models, informed by historical data, provide a potent tool for timely intervention and data-driven policy formulation.

Our endeavour extends to a meticulous examination of the composition of mixed gas interactions, focusing on key pollutants such as carbon monoxide, nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide, methane, and ammonia. By examining their combined impact on chemical product formation, the project offers valuable insights into the harmfulness of resultant products. These insights are translated into actionable information through user-friendly interactive dashboards, enhancing accessibility for the public, policymakers, and stakeholders.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The study conducted in paper [1] comprehensively analyses air pollution data from 23 Indian cities over a six-year period. The dataset undergoes thorough cleaning and preprocessing, encompassing the handling of NAN values, treatment of outliers, and the normalization of data values. A correlation-based feature selection technique is employed to filter pollutants affecting AQI, and skewed features are subjected to logarithmic transformations. Exploratory data analysis methods uncover hidden patterns within the dataset, notably observing a significant decline in pollutants during 2020. Data imbalance is effectively mitigated through SMOTE analysis, leading to the partitioning of the dataset into 75% training and 25% testing subsets. Machine learning-based AQI prediction is conducted with and without SMOTE resampling, with the XGBoost model achieving the highest accuracy for both training and testing sets. Classical statistical error metrics assess and compare model performance. This research contributes significantly to air quality analysis and prediction for India, with potential extensions involving the incorporation of deep learning techniques for AQI prediction.

The study conducted in paper [2] found that the anticipation of the air quality index is achieved by employing various algorithms, including linear regression, Decision Tree, and Random Forest. From the results obtained, it has been inferred that a superior prediction of the air quality index is provided by the Random Forest algorithm. This conclusion is based on the analysis of the data and the comparison of predictive performance, with Random Forest consistently outperforming the other methods in

terms of accuracy and reliability. The enhanced predictive capabilities of the Random Forest algorithm make it the preferred choice for forecasting air quality index, as it offers more robust and dependable results, thus contributing to a more effective and accurate assessment of air quality conditions.

According to a recent study by Reshma J in paper [3], Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) acts as a robust method for forecasting air pollutants. The study consistently demonstrates the precision of ANN in forecasting vital air pollutants, encompassing SO₂, NO₂, O₃, CO, and particulate matter. Moreover, the model's incorporation of meteorological parameters, including temperature, relative humidity, absolute humidity, and wind direction, enhances its predictive capabilities of the model. An additional advantage of the ANN approach is its adaptability to web applications, offering end-users real-time access to air quality information. This empowers individuals to proactively address air pollution's adverse effects, ultimately safeguarding public health and the environment.

In summary, the study in paper [4] highlights the health risks of prolonged exposure to particulate matter and the rising global pollution levels, including in Russia. Effective environmental measures and predictive monitoring are essential. The research demonstrates the successful use of machine learning methods. However, long-term forecasts are limited due to data quality constraints. More high-quality data is needed, especially in Russian cities, where it remains scarce. This underscores the need for improved air quality monitoring and public awareness efforts, which would expand data resources, enhance machine learning models, and enable more accurate air quality predictions. Increasing the number of air quality monitoring centers in Russia and providing free public access to this information is crucial.

Following the completion of the study in paper [5], the research team achieved success in crafting an Ensemble learning model with the ability to forecast forthcoming air pollution concentrations. This was accomplished by amalgamating basic learning models and employing a meta-learner to generate the ultimate predictions for air pollution concentrations. The researchers also conducted a comprehensive assessment of various machine learning algorithms' performance in forecasting future APC values. The proposed air quality prediction algorithm, which combines Recursive Air Quality Predictor (RAQP) with ensemble learning, exhibited improved results for Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂) and Ozone (O₃), with relatively similar outcomes for Fine Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}) and Carbon Monoxide (CO). Regarding Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), the proposed model outperformed across all APCs.

According to the study in paper [6], a novel technique was introduced for gas sensing and classification using machine learning (ML) algorithms. This approach accurately classified combinations of three gases with up to 97% accuracy by analyzing autocorrelation Functions (ACFs) and their impedance characteristics. Despite the high dimensionality of the classifier, researchers successfully identified unique features related to gas molecules, such as polarity, molecular weight, and adsorption, allowing precise classification, especially in complex scenarios involving gas mixtures. This cost-effective and lightweight method demonstrates promise for gas mixture classification.

To enhance prediction accuracy for mixed gases, this paper [7] introduces a novel regression prediction model, TCN, known for its robust time series pattern recognition capabilities. The model is enhanced in two key ways: firstly, by modifying its structure to incorporate additional channels within its residual network for improved information retrieval at each step, and secondly, by optimizing its activation function, which is determined through experimental validation. The results demonstrate the superiority of this approach over LSTM, GRU, and generic TCN in regression prediction tests for two gas mixtures. This method holds

promise for effective gas mixture analysis when applied to E-nose systems. In future work, further improvements will be explored to enhance TCN's performance, potentially through synergistic combinations with other neural networks.

In this paper [8], the authors propose enhancements to machine olfactory systems. They introduce a dynamic time warping algorithm (DTW) that significantly improves classification accuracy by 26.87%. Through original feature construction and the PCA method, the classification accuracy rate increases by 25.8%. Furthermore, the time efficiency of the random forest algorithm is boosted using the extreme random tree algorithm, resulting in a final classification accuracy of 99.28%. Notably, the runtime is substantially reduced to only 103.2568 s, marking a 66.85% decrease from the random forest algorithm. This paper effectively addresses the classification challenges of mixed gases, enhances the random forest algorithm, and provides a theoretical foundation for simulating the olfactory nervous system.

III. OBJECTIVES

- 1) *Visualization*: Create a web-based platform that provides visualization of air quality data, including pollutant concentrations and air quality indices for various locations in India.
- 2) *Mixed Gas Analysis*: Develop analytical techniques to assess the composition of mixed gases in the air, emphasizing the identification of pollutants and their sources, enabling more informed decision-making.
- 3) *Pollution Prediction*: Implement predictive models that use historical data, meteorological factors, and pollutant trends to forecast air quality, allowing for early warnings and timely intervention.
- 4) *Precision Air Quality Predictions*: Enhance the precision of pollution forecasts by utilizing advanced data analytics and machine learning, ensuring location-specific accuracy.

IV. DATASETS

The dataset utilized in this project was collected from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) of India, a leading authority in monitoring and regulating environmental pollution. The dataset comprises a comprehensive collection of air quality metrics and pollutant data sourced from various monitoring stations across India.

Timestamp	PM2.5 (µg/m³)	PM10 (µg/m³)	NO (µg/m³)	NO2 (µg/m³)	NOx (ppb)	NH3 (µg/m³)	SO2 (µg/m³)	CO (mg/m³)	Ozone (µg/m³)	Benzene (µg/m³)	Toluene (µg/m³)	AT (°C)	RH (%)	WD (deg)	BP (mmHg)	
2023-12-31 00:00:00	47.90625	103.1666666667	2.4864583333	8.6656258	64548611111	9.6625	11.6399205556	0.298368055556	7.7540909090909	0.178125	1.1784722222222	22.30104	82.31944	123.3506944	728.2395833333	
2023-12-30 00:00:00	32.229166666667	77.90625	2.5572916667	8.0958333333	8.88437510	4.3229166667	12.4326388889	0.313229166667	7.7540909090909	0.213095238095238	1.2364583333333	23.325	82.9375	128.2291667	728.4095833333	
2023-12-29 00:00:00	40.666666666667	82.5208333333	2.5125	9.7218759	26770833333	10.8604166667	10.4635416667	0.36270833333	7.7540909090909	0.227651515151515	1.43229166666667	22.34583	82.98958	126.9895833	728.8854166667	
2023-12-28 00:00:00	46.416666666667	96.2916666667	2.51259	4.2083333333	0.09895833333	11.10625	11.0618055556	0.362291666667	7.7540909090909	0.21666666666667	1.43229166666667	22.72396	82.92708	121.7395833	728.8333333333	
2023-12-27 00:00:00	39.03125	85.7916666667	2.5864583333	3.3645833333	9.17511	12.395833333	14.7024205556	0.268263888889	7.7540909090909	0.190789473684211	1.068402277777778	22.69167	82.95833	127.78125	729.5104166667	
2023-12-26 00:00:00	44.145833333333	93.28125	2.45625	9.059375	8.82510	8.5416666667	8.82510	8.5416666667	0.296041666667	7.7540909090909	0.190909090909091	1.1715277777778	23.04271	82.88542	136.9479167	729.375
2023-12-25 00:00:00	44.5	85.9583333333	2.5239583333	9.0416666667	8.84687510	16.145833333	15.4409722222	0.46847222222	13.7678125	0.26875	1.8440972222222	22.80625	82.92708	128.6979167	729.53125	
2023-12-24 00:00:00	73.28125	131.3645833333	2.4913194444	0.02986111111	8.862510	4.5694444444	12.0690972222	0.329791666667	25.6756944444444	0.198958333333333	1.3034722222222	22.59583	81.48958	126.9340278	729.6041666667	
2023-12-23 00:00:00	88.0652173913044	204.471014493	2.530357142910	4.6071428571	6.803571428613	9.1428571429	13.6486111111	0.4838888888889	26.158571428571	0.283680555555555	1.907986111111111	22.78472	80.51042	119.3229167	728.7361111111	
2023-12-22 00:00:00	73.927083333333	135.1875	2.5044875	8.8796875	8.8125	10.734375	11.5605072464	0.582934782609	29.08640625	0.339130434782609	2.3043478260896	23.71667	82.8125	148.728	3043478261	
2023-12-21 00:00:00	64.104166666667	113.1145833333	2.5783333333	10.737777778	9.061111111111111	16.555555556	19.0545138889	0.794409722222	26.899055555556	0.4465277777778	3.140625	22.62292	81.38889	144.3611111	728.5	
2023-12-20 00:00:00	77.583333333333	129.822916667	2.5120833333	9.0458	9.0291666667	10.9545833333	11.9145833333	0.564965277778	30.972	0.313541666666667	2.228819444444444	22.44167	82.68056	131.0555556	728.5	
2023-12-19 00:00:00	83.0681818181818	138.806818182	2.54294871799	6.692307692319	2.775641025613	0.3846153846	17.3105072464	0.73876811594	26.237307692308	0.415217391304348	2.85978260896565	22.96563	82.14583	127.9236111	728.4492753623	
2023-12-18 00:00:00	57.1590909090909	94.4659090909	2.46	8.4975	8.5225	9.525	16.9387681159	0.590579710145	24.0775	0.351883939393939	2.33550724637681	21.79896	82.76389	121.7742056	728.1195652174	
2023-12-17 00:00:00	39.3125	88.1875	2.5475694444	5.9652777778	4.1215277778	6.4190972222	14.878125	0.5706944444444	23.146493055556	0.326388888888889	2.251388888888889	22.40729	82.59722	132.7465278	727.7361111111	
2023-12-16 00:00:00	32.2608695652174	81.4318181818	2.56423611115	4.6597222222	4.9944444444	18.0770833333	15.8097222222	0.651284722222	21.851597222222	0.364583333333333	2.577083333333333	23.1	82.19792	123.0138889	728.0729166667	
2023-12-15 00:00:00	63.90625	113.572916667	2.55	5.1906254	8.3229166667	11.4158333333	11.2461805556	0.377118055556	23.64520833333	0.243253968253968	1.486458333333333	22.03958	81.125	130.4270833	728.625	

Fig 1 Dataset before predicting AQI

Timestamp	PM2.5 (µg/m³)	PM10 (µg/m³)	NO (µg/m³)	NO2 (µg/m³)	NOx (ppb)	NH3 (µg/m³)	SO2 (µg/m³)	CO (mg/m³)	Ozone (µg/m³)	Benzene (µg/m³)	Toluene (µg/m³)	AT (°C)	RH (%)	WD (deg)	BP (mmHg)	AQI
2023-12-31 00:00:00	47.90625	103.166666667	2.48645833333	8.6656258	64548611111	9.6625	11.6398305556	0.298380855556	7.75409090909	0.178125	1.17847222222	22.30104	82.31944	123.3506944	728.239583333	102.111111111
2023-12-30 00:00:00	32.22916666667	77.90625	2.55729166667	8.89833333333	8.88437510	4.32291666667	12.4326388889	0.313229166667	7.75409090909	0.213095238095238	1.23645833333333	23.325	82.9375	128.2291667	728.489583333	77.90625
2023-12-29 00:00:00	40.66666666667	82.5208333333	2.5125	9.7218759	267708333310	8.60416666667	10.46354166667	0.362708333333	7.75409090909	0.227651515151515	1.432291666666667	22.34583	82.98958	126.9895833	728.88541666667	82.5208333333
2023-12-28 00:00:00	46.41666666667	96.229166667	2.51259	4.20833333333	0.90958333333	11.10625	11.0618055556	0.362291666667	7.75409090909	0.216666666666667	1.432291666666667	22.72396	82.92708	121.7395833	728.833333333	96.2291666667
2023-12-27 00:00:00	39.03125	85.7916666667	2.58645833339	3.36458333333		9.17511	12.2395833333	14.7024305556	0.286263888889	0.190789473684211	1.068402777777778	22.69167	82.95833	127.78125	728.51041666667	85.7916666667
2023-12-26 00:00:00	44.14583333333	93.28125	2.45625	9.059375	8.82510	8.54166666667	11.5326805556	0.29641666667	7.75409090909	0.1909090909091	1.171527777777778	23.04271	82.88542	136.9479167	729.375	93.28125
2023-12-25 00:00:00	44.5	85.9583333333	2.52395833338	9.04166666667		8.84687510	16.145833333	15.4409722222	0.46847222222	13.7678125	0.26875	1.8440972222222	22.80625	82.92708	128.6979167	729.53125
2023-12-24 00:00:00	73.28125	131.364583333	2.49131944449	0.29861111111		8.862510	45.694444444	12.0690972222	0.329791666667	25.6756944444444	0.198958333333333	1.3034722222222	22.59583	81.48958	126.9340278	729.60416666667
2023-12-23 00:00:00	88.0652173913044	204.471014493	2.530357142910	4.60714285719	6.603571428613	9.1428571429	13.6486111111	0.483888888889	26.158571428571	0.283680555555555	1.907986111111111	22.78472	80.51042	119.3229167	728.736111111	193.5507246377
2023-12-22 00:00:00	73.9270833333333	135.1875	2.5046875	8.8798875	8.8125	10.734375	11.5605072464	0.582934782609	29.08640625	0.339130434782609	2.304347826096096	23.71667	82.8125	148.728	304.3478261	146.423611111
2023-12-21 00:00:00	64.1041666666667	113.114583333	2.578333333310	7.377777778	9.06111111111	13.1655555556	19.0545138889	0.794409722222	26.899055555556	0.446527777777778	3.140625	22.62292	81.38889	144.3611111	728.5113	680.5555556
2023-12-20 00:00:00	71.5833333333333	129.822916667	2.51208333333			9.0458	90.291666667	10.95458333333	11.91458333333	30.972	0.312541666666667	22.228819444444444	22.54467	82.68058	131.9555556	728.5158
2023-12-19 00:00:00	83.0681818181818	138.806818182	2.54294871799	6.692307692319	2.775641025613	0.3846153846	17.3105072464	0.723876811594	26.23767692308	0.415217391304348	2.85978260869565	22.96563	82.14583	127.9229167	728.4492753623	176.8939393939
2023-12-18 00:00:00	57.1590909090909	94.4659090909	2.46	8.4975	8.5225	9.525	16.9387681159	0.590579710145	24.0775	0.3518939393939	2.33550724637681	21.79896	82.76389	121.7743056	728.1195652174	95.26515151515
2023-12-17 00:00:00	39.3125	88.1875	2.54756944445	5.96527777778	4.121527777816	41.909722222	14.878125	0.570094444444	23.146483055556	0.326388888888889	2.251388888888889	22.40729	82.59722	132.9465278	727.736111111	88.1875
2023-12-16 00:00:00	32.2608695652174	81.4318181818	2.56423611115	4.659722222224	9.94444444444	18.07708333333	15.8097222222	0.651284722222	21.85159722222	0.364583333333333	2.57708333333333	23.1	82.18792	123.0138889	728.0729166667	81.4318181818
2023-12-15 00:00:00	63.90625	113.572916667	2.55	5.1906254	8322916666717	41.4583333333	11.2461805556	0.377118055556	23.6445208333333	0.242253968253968	1.486458333333333	22.03958	81.125	130.4270833	728.625	113.0283333333

Fig 2 Dataset after predicting AQI

Id.No	Reaction	Gas Involved	Product Formed	Percentage Contribution	SO2 contribution	NO2 contribution	NH3 contribution	CO contribution	CO contribution	Si harmful
1	CO + NO2 → CO2 + NO	CO, NO2	Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Nitric oxide (NO)	CO: 17.84%, NO2: 62.16%	0	62.16	0	0	0	17.84%
2	CO + NH3 → HCN + H2O	CO, NH3	Hydrogen cyanide (HCN) + Water (H2O)	CO: 62.22%, NH3: 37.78%	0	0	37.78	0	0	62.22%
3	NO2 + NH3 → H2O + NO + S	NO2, NH3	Water (H2O) + Nitrogen Oxide (NO) + Sulfur	NO2: 79.81%, NH3: 20.99%	79.81	0	20.99	0	0	0%
4	2CO + 4C2H6 → 3C2H4 + 2H2O	CO, C2H6	Ethylene (C2H4) + Water (H2O)	CO: 46.87%, C2H6: 53.13%	0	0	0	53.13	0	46.87%
5	NO2 + NO2 → SO2 + SO	NO2, NO2	Sulfur trioxide (SO3) + Nitric oxide (NO)	NO2: 55.18%, NO2: 41.82%	55.18	41.82	0	0	0	0%
6	NH3 + C2H4 → HCN + H2	NH3, C2H4	Hydrogen cyanide (HCN) + Hydrogen (H2)	NH3: 51.52%, C2H4: 48.48%	0	0	51.52	48.48	0	0%
7	NO2 + 2CO → COB + 2CO2	NO2, CO	Carbonyl sulfide (COS) + Carbon dioxide (CO2)	NO2: 43.24%, CO: 56.76%	43.24	0	0	0	0	56.76%
8	HCO + 2NO2 → 4CO2 + N2	CO, NO2	Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Nitrogen (N2)	CO: 54.80%, NO2: 45.10%	0	45.1	0	0	0	54.80%
9	C2H4 + 2NO2 → CO2 + 2H2O + N2	C2H4, NO2	Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Water (H2O) + Nitrogen (N2)	C2H4: 14.41%, NO2: 85.19%	0	85.19	0	0	14.41	0%
10	2NH3 + 4NO2 → 7N2 + 12H2O	NH3, NO2	Nitrogen (N2) + Water (H2O)	NH3: 33.01%, NO2: 66.99%	0	66.99	33.01	0	0	0%
11	3CO + 2NO2 → 3CO2 + N2O	CO, NO2	Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Nitrous oxide (N2O)	CO: 47.73%, NO2: 52.27%	0	52.27	0	0	0	47.73%
12	CO + 2NO2 → CO2 + N2O3	CO, NO2	Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Dinitrogen trioxide (N2O3)	CO: 23.33%, NO2: 76.67%	0	76.67	0	0	0	23.33%
13	2C2H4 + 3NO2 → 2CO + 4H2O + 3H	C2H4, NO2	Carbon monoxide (CO) + Water (H2O) + Sulfur (S)	C2H4: 14.29%, NO2: 85.71%	85.71	0	0	0	14.29	0%
14	4NH3 + 3NO2 → 7N2O + 6H2O	NH3, NO2	Nitrous oxide (N2O) + Water (H2O)	NH3: 21.30%, NO2: 78.70%	0	78.7	21.3	0	0	0%
15	2NH3 + 4NO2 → 7N2 + 12H2O	NH3, NO2	Nitrogen (N2) + Water (H2O)	NH3: 33.01%, NO2: 66.99%	0	66.99	33.01	0	0	0%
16	3CO + 4NH3 → 3CO2 + 2N2	CO, NH3	Methane (CH4) + Nitrogen (N2)	CO: 55.24%, NH3: 44.76%	0	0	44.74	0	0	55.24%
17	3CO + NO2 → COB + 2CO2	CO, NO2	Carbonyl sulfide (COS) + Carbon dioxide (CO2)	CO: 56.76%, NO2: 43.24%	43.24	0	0	0	0	56.76%
18	NH3 + 2CO → HCN + CO2 + H2	NH3, CO	Hydrogen cyanide (HCN) + Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Hydrogen (H2)	NH3: 23.29%, CO: 76.71%	0	0	23.29	0	0	76.71%
19	3CO + 2NO2 → N2O3 + 3CO2	CO, NO2	Nitrous oxide (N2O) + Sulfur trioxide (SO3)	NO2: 67.61%, NO2: 32.39%	67.61	32.39	0	0	0	0%
20	2CO + NO2 → 2CO2 + S	CO, NO2	Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Sulfur (S)	CO: 46.87%, NO2: 53.13%	53.13	0	0	0	0	46.87%
21	C2H4 + 4NO2 → CO2 + 2H2O + 4NO	C2H4, NO2	Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Water (H2O) + Nitric oxide (NO)	C2H4: 9%, NO2: 91%	0	91	0	0	0	0%
22	CO + 2NO2 → CO2 + N2O3	CO, NO2	Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Dinitrogen trioxide (N2O3)	CO: 23.33%, NO2: 76.67%	0	76.67	0	0	0	23.33%
23	6NH3 + 8NO2 → 7N2O + 8H2O	NH3, NO2	Nitrous oxide (N2O) + Water (H2O)	NH3: 21.70%, NO2: 78.30%	0	78.3	21.7	0	0	0%
24	2C2H4 + 3NO2 → 2CO + 4H2O + 3S	C2H4, NO2	Carbon monoxide (CO) + Water (H2O) + Sulfur (S)	C2H4: 14.29%, NO2: 85.71%	85.71	0	0	0	14.29	0%
25	3CO + 2NO2 → 3CO2 + N2O	CO, NO2	Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Nitrous oxide (N2O)	CO: 47.73%, NO2: 52.27%	0	52.27	0	0	0	47.73%
26	4NH3 + 6NO2 → 7N2 + 12H2O	NH3, NO2	Nitrogen (N2) + Water (H2O)	NH3: 19.77%, NO2: 80.23%	0	80.23	19.77	0	0	0%
27	2NO2 + C2H4 → 2H2O + 3CO + N2	NO2, C2H4	Water (H2O) + Carbon dioxide (CO2) + Nitrogen (N2)	NO2: 55.19%, C2H4: 14.81%	0	55.19	0	0	14.81	0%
28	2NH3 + 8NO2 → 5N2O + 3H2O	NH3, NO2	Nitrous oxide (N2O), Water (H2O)	NH3: 12.41%, NO2: 87.59%	0	0	12.41	0	0	0%
29	CO2 + 2NH3 → H2O + OC(NH)2	NH3, CO2	Water (H2O), Urea (OC(NH)2)	CO2: 50.41%, NH3: 49.59%	0	0	49.59	0	0	0%
30	4NH3 + SO2 → 2N2 + H2O	NH3, SO2	Nitrogen (N2), Water (H2O)	NH3: 41.48%, SO2: 58.54%	0	0	41.48	0	0	0%

Fig 3 Dataset for Mixed Gas Analysis

V METHODOLOGIES

The project delves into a meticulous analysis of the composition of mixed gases in the atmosphere, unravelling their sources and contributions to air pollution. Through the integrated application of data analysis, machine learning, and web development, this study strives to bridge the gap between environmental data and actionable solutions, making a significant contribution to the mitigation of air pollution and the enhancement of environmental health in India. Visualizing air quality prediction with mixed gas analysis using machine learning involves creating informative and insightful visual representations of the predictive model's outputs and their relationships with input variables. Here is a detailed methodology for this process:

A. Visualization of Air Quality Prediction.

- 1) Data Collection:** Comprehensive datasets are gathered from the CPCB, covering air quality measurements, mixed gas concentrations, and meteorological information. This step ensures the dataset's robustness and representation of various environmental conditions.
- 2) Preprocessing:** Raw data undergoes rigorous preprocessing to address missing values, outliers, and data integrity issues. This step is crucial for ensuring the quality of the dataset and laying a solid foundation for subsequent analyses and modeling efforts.
- 3) Normalization and Feature Extraction:** Techniques such as Min-Max scaling are employed for normalization to ensure consistent scaling for fair comparisons. Feature extraction is also performed to identify key variables crucial for predictive models, thereby enhancing model performance by reducing dimensionality and focusing on critical features.

4) *Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)*: EDA is conducted to gain insights into data distribution, temporal patterns, and feature correlations through visualizations like histograms and scatter plots. This analysis provides essential insights for the development of predictive models.

5) *Predictive Modeling*: Thorough preprocessing and feature engineering inform the selection and training of predictive models such as linear regression, decision trees, random forests, and XGBoost. Model evaluation metrics guide the selection of the most effective model.

6) *Website Creation*: A combination of tools and technologies was utilized to ensure an engaging user experience. Plotly was employed to seamlessly embed interactive visualizations into the website, providing users with dynamic insights. Additionally, Power BI played a key role in crafting comprehensive dashboards, enabling users to easily interpret and analyze data. The overall design of the website was meticulously crafted using HTML and CSS, ensuring a visually appealing and user-friendly interface.

Fig 4 shows the methodological steps adopted in the process of visualizing air quality prediction.

Fig 4 Air Quality Prediction

Fig 5 Mixed Gas Analysis

B. Proposed Algorithm

Random Forest Algorithm (RFA): Random Forest algorithm can be effectively used in air quality prediction due to its ability to handle complex and nonlinear relationships between input variables and target outputs. Here's how Random Forest can be applied in air quality prediction:

- 1) *Data Preprocessing*: The first step involves gathering air quality data from various sources such as monitoring stations, weather stations, and satellite data. This data may include features such as pollutant concentrations (e.g., PM2.5, PM10, NO₂, SO₂), meteorological factors (e.g., temperature, humidity, wind speed), geographical features, and temporal factors.
- 2) *Data Cleaning and Feature Engineering*: Once the data is collected, it needs to be cleaned to handle missing values, outliers, and inconsistencies. Feature engineering techniques can be applied to extract relevant features or derive new features that capture important patterns in the data.
- 3) *Splitting Data*: The dataset is then split into training and testing sets. The training set is used to train the Random Forest model, while the testing set is used to evaluate its performance.
- 4) *Model Training*: The Random Forest algorithm is applied to the training data. Random Forest is an ensemble learning method that builds multiple decision trees during training. Each tree is trained on a random subset of the features and a random subset of the training data. The final prediction is then made by aggregating the predictions of all the individual trees.
- 5) *Model Evaluation*: Once the model is trained, it is evaluated using the testing set. Common evaluation metrics for regression tasks in air quality prediction include Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and R-squared (R²) score.
- 6) *Hyperparameter Tuning*: Hyperparameters of the Random Forest algorithm, such as the number of trees in the forest and the maximum depth of each tree, can be tuned using techniques like grid search or random search to optimize model performance.
- 7) *Prediction*: After the model is trained and evaluated, it can be deployed to make predictions on new or unseen data. These predictions can provide valuable insights into future air quality conditions, which can be used for decision-making and pollution control efforts.

C. Mixed Gas Analysis

- 1) *Data Sources*: The data was collected from various online platforms and chemistry resources.
- 2) *Data Processing*: The collected data includes different chemical reactions, which were then balanced to ensure accurate representation.
- 3) *Calculations*: Using established chemical equations and stoichiometry, the contribution of each gas to the formation of products was calculated.

Contribution of each gases in the formation of the product:

Equation: $\text{CO} + \text{NH}_3 \rightarrow \text{HCN} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$

Determine the molecular weights:

- 1) Molecular weight of CO: $12(\text{C})+16(\text{O})=28\text{g/mol}$
- 2) Molecular weight of NH₃: $14(\text{N})+3(\text{H})=14+3=17\text{g/mol}$

Calculate the mass of each reactant:

1 mole of CO reacts with 1 mole of NH₃:

- 1) Mass of CO: $1\text{mole}\times 28\text{g/mol}=28\text{g}$
- 2) Mass of NH₃: $1\text{mole}\times 17\text{g/mol}=17\text{g}$

Calculate the total mass of the reactants:

- 1) Total mass of reactants: $28\text{g}(\text{CO})+17\text{g}(\text{NH}_3)=45\text{g}$

Calculate the contribution of each reactant:

1) Contribution of CO: $(28/45) \times 100 = 62.22$

2) Contribution of NH₃: $(17/45) \times 100 = 37.78$

So, the contributions of gases in the equation "CO + NH₃ → HCN + H₂O" are:

1) Contribution of CO: 62.22%

2) Contribution of NH₃: 37.78%

4) *Harmfulness Assessment*: The harmfulness of each product was determined by evaluating the thresholds of the gases involved and the nature of the products formed. These thresholds and product characteristics were sourced from Scientific Literature.

OR(

SO₂ >= 5%, // SO₂ contribution threshold

NO >= 5%, // NO₂ contribution threshold

CH₄ >= 20%, // CH₄ contribution threshold

CO >= 10%, // CO contribution threshold

NH₃ >= 10% // NH₃ contribution threshold

),

"Yes", // If any gas exceeds the threshold

"No" // Otherwise

5) *Visualization*: Python libraries and Power BI were used to create visualizations that effectively communicate the data and its implications. The visualizations were deployed on a dedicated website.

Fig 5 shows the steps involved in mixed gas analysis.

VI.

RESU
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Metrics	Proposed Model (Random Forest)	Decision Tree	Xgboost	Linear Regression	Lasso Regression	KNN
MAE	2.25812	2.750	2.954	7.803	7.954	5.177
MSE	149.416	136.979	195.019	185.764	172.333	167.627
RMSE	12.224	11.704	13.965	13.629	13.128	12.947

Fig 6 Evaluation Matrix

Fig 7 Line Graph for all features over time

Fig 8 Dashboard for Air Quality Visualization

Fig 9 Percentage Contribution of Gases in CO Reactions

Fig 10 Pie Chart of Percentage Contribution of CO In Reactions

Scatter Plot of Gases Involved with CO reactions and Product Formed

Fig 11 Scatter Plot of Gases Involved with CO reactions and Product Formed

Fig 12 Dashboard for Mixed Gas Analysis

VII. CONCLUSION

Our project addresses the critical issue of air pollution by leveraging data analysis and cutting-edge technology. Through meticulous analysis of air quality metrics and pollutant data from the CPCB website of India, we have identified key pollutants and delineated pollution trends. The integration of mixed gas analysis has provided valuable insights into current air quality conditions. Moving forward, the development of a user-friendly website with interactive dashboards ensures accessibility to the public, policymakers, and stakeholders, providing actionable insights for informed decision-making. By harnessing machine learning algorithms and conducting in-depth analysis of mixed gas interactions, we have made significant strides in forecasting air quality trends and assessing environmental impact. Our future enhancements will include implementing real-time data acquisition to enhance the accuracy and timeliness of air quality forecasts, refining machine learning models to improve predictive capabilities and adaptability to changing environmental conditions, and deepening our understanding of mixed gas interactions through ongoing research and collaboration with experts. Additionally, we aim to expand the scope and impact of the project through collaboration with governmental agencies, research institutions, and environmental organizations, fostering partnerships and sharing insights to collectively work towards mitigating the adverse effects of air pollution and creating a healthier, more sustainable environment for current and future generations.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. Kumar, B.P Pande, "**Air pollution prediction with machine learning: a case study of Indian cities**", Iranian Society of Environmentalists (IRSEN) and Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University. International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology (2023) 20:5333–5348 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-022-04241-5>
- [2] Ritik Sharma, Gaurav Shilimkar, Shivam Pisal, "**Air Quality Prediction by Machine Learning**", Vishwakarma Institute of Technology, Pune, Maharashtra, India. International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.32628/IJSRST218396>
- [3] Reshma J, "**Analysis and Prediction of Air Quality**", Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, BNM Institute of Technology, Bengaluru, India. International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) Volume: 07 Issue: 01 | Jan 2020 e-ISSN: 2395-0056 p-ISSN: 2395-0072 Available at: www.irjet.net
- [4] Ekaterina Gladkova, Liliya Saychenko, "**Applying machine learning techniques in air quality prediction**", Saint Petersburg Mining University, St Petersburg, Russia. X International Scientific Siberian Transport Forum. Available at: www.sciencedirect.com

[5] Dionis A. Padilla, Glenn V. Magwili, Luis Benjamin Z. Mercado, Jean Tristan L. Reyes, "**Air Quality Prediction using Recurrent Air Quality Predictor with Ensemble Learning**", School of Electrical, Electronics, and Computer Engineering, Mapua University Philippines.

Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp>

[6] Kookjin Lee(1), Sangjin Nam(2), Hyojun Kim(3)*, Dae-Young Jeon(4), Dongha Shin(3), Hyeong-Gyun Lim(3), Chulmin Kim(1), Doyoon Kim(1), Yeonsu Kim(1), Sang-Hoon Byeon(3), and Gyu-Tae Kim(1), "**Detection and Accurate Classification of Mixed Gases Using Machine Learning with Impedance Data**",

1. School of Electrical Engineering Korea University, Republic of Korea

2. Dept of Computer Science and Engineering Korea University, Republic of Korea

3. Dept of Environmental Health College of Health Sciences Korea University, Republic of Korea. * Samsung Electronics Co. Ltd Samsung-ro Yongin-si, Republic of Korea

4. Institute of Advanced Composite Materials Korea Institute of Science and Technology, Republic of Korea

Available at: www.advtheorysimul.com

[7] Liwen Zeng (1), Yang Xu (2), Sen Ni (1) Min Xu (3), Pengfei Jia (1), "**A mixed gas concentration regression prediction method for electronic nose based on two-channel TCN**".

1. School of Electrical Engineering, Guangxi University, Nanning, China.

2. Guangxi Key Laboratory of Intelligent Control and Maintenance of Power Equipment, Guangxi University, Nanning, China.

3. College of Food Science and Bioengineering, Xihua University, Chengdu, China.

Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/sensors-and-actuators-b-chemical>

[8] Yonghui Xu (1), Xi Zhao (1), Yinsheng Chen (2) and Zixuan Yang (1), "**Research on a Mixed Gas Classification Algorithm Based on Extreme Random Tree**",

1. School of Electrical Engineering and Automation, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin 150001, China.

2. School of Measurement and Control Technology and Communication Engineering, Harbin University of Science and Technology, Harbin 150001, China.

Available at: www.mdpi.com/journal/applsci